

CONCEPT OF METAPHOR AND ITS PROPERTIES

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Abstract. *In this article I focused on metaphor and its features. We know that Uzbek writers and poets have interpreted and researched a lot about metaphor. In this article, I would like to explain them to you in English. This article can be used by young scientists, research students. the reason is that in their scientific work and during their creative research, they will have to use the word in a different sense. If they know the word metaphor and its basic meaning well, they can freely use it in their works. The article first presents examples from simple metaphors to mixed and extended metaphors. In order to make it more understandable for the reader, I have chosen the most popular expressions when choosing examples. Thanks, enjoy the information.*

Key words: *Metaphor, simple metaphor, mixed and extended metaphor, figurative meaning, Uzbek metaphors and English metaphors.*

ПОНЯТИЕ МЕТАФОРЫ И ЕЕ СВОЙСТВА

Аннотация. *В этой статье я сосредоточился на метафоре и ее особенностях. Мы знаем, что узбекские писатели и поэты много интерпретировали и исследовали метафору. В этой статье я хотел бы объяснить их вам на английском языке. Данная статья может быть использована молодыми учеными, студентами-исследователями. причина в том, что в своей научной работе и во время своего творческого поиска им придется употреблять это слово в ином смысле. Если они хорошо знают слово метафора и его основное значение, то могут свободно использовать его в своих произведениях. В статье сначала представлены примеры от простых метафор до смешанных и расширенных метафор. Для того, чтобы сделать его более понятным для читателя, при подборе примеров я выбрал самые популярные выражения. Спасибо, наслаждайтесь информацией.*

Ключевые слова: *Метафора, простая метафора, смешанная и расширенная метафора, переносное значение, узбекские метафоры и английские метафоры.*

INTRODUCTION

Metaphor is greek - move, transfer) ad. Using a word or phrase in a figurative sense based on analogy or analogy and a word or phrase used in such a sense; metaphor, metaphor (may., the meaning of the word "ear" in the combinations "head of the street" and "the head of the street" is based on a metaphor).

A metaphor is a figure of speech that makes a comparison between two different things that have something important in common. The word "metaphor" comes from the Greek word metaphor which means "to move" or "to walk across". Metaphors mean "a word, image, idea, or situation that has a different meaning."

Dr. Gregory's House (from the old TV series At Home, MD): "I'm a night owl, Wilson's an early bird, we're a different species," he said metaphorically. "Then take him to his cafe," said Dr. Cuddy, extending the metaphor of the bird of the house—"Who can clean the belly out of me?" - he said.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Calling someone a "night owl" or an "early bird" is a common (or traditional) example of metaphor that is often easily understood by native speakers. Let's look at different ways of using the

same traditional metaphor. A metaphor is a literary or rhetorical figure that uses the characteristics of another object or action to explain an object or action. That is, he uses an analogy to better explain the idea he is trying to get across.

For example: Your hair is the morning sun.

"His hair" is the object he is trying to explain, and "they are the morning sun" is an analogy with the hair being very yellow or golden in color.

Thus, the following concepts are derived from the metaphor:

- helps to explain the idea with the help of comparison.
- It should not be taken literally (hair cannot be the sun), but yes in a symbolic sense.
- They are used a lot in poetry or literature. This means that it is usually intended to embellish the concept (Every star in the sky is a tear I cried for you).
- They can also be used as an exaggerated form of expression without considering the concept of beauty (This post killed me).

Simple metaphors

Some metaphors are so common that we can't even see that they are metaphors. Take, for example, the well-known metaphor of life as a journey. We find it in advertising slogans:

- "Life is a journey, a good journey."

(United Airlines)

- "Life is a journey".

(Nissan)

- "The journey never stops."

(American Express)

- "Life is a journey"

(Hugo Boss Perfume)

Metaphors in Literature and Popular Culture

RESEARCH RESULTS

Perhaps one of the most commonly cited examples of a metaphor in English literature is Shakespeare's "All the world's a stage" monologue from "As You Like It":

"All the world's a stage,
And all the men and women merely players;
They have their exits and their entrances..."

One reason this metaphor is effective is that each line contains a separate metaphor, but all come together as part of a single, broader idea—that life itself is like a stage play. Some other examples of metaphors in literature and popular culture include:

"You are the sunshine of my life...And if I thought our love was ending, I'd find myself drowning in my own tears." -Stevie Wonder

"I finally asked you to dance on the last slow song, beneath the moon that was really a disco ball." -Lady Antebellum

"The sky was a purple bruise, the ground was iron, and you fell all around the town until you looked the same." -Elvis Costello

"You ain't nothing but a hound dog." -Made famous by Elvis Presley, but written by Jerry Leiber and Mike Stoller

"A hospital bed is a parked taxi with the meter running." -Groucho Marx

"Dying is a wild night and a new road." -Emily Dickinson

"Time rises and rises, and when it reaches the level of your eyes you drown." -Margaret Atwood

"I'm a little pencil in the hand of a writing God." -Mother Teresa

"Books are the mirrors of the soul." -Virginia Woolf

Each of these metaphors works in different ways, but they all force the reader to think about what they mean. Once the reader is able to make a connection to the metaphor, the meaning becomes very clear. Take that last line, for instance. Imagining a mirror that can look into your soul evokes a powerful image of the impact books can have.

Mixed and Extended Metaphors

Like most literary devices, metaphors can be ineffective when misused. They end up either confusing the reader or drawing attention to the author's lack of skill. A mixed metaphor moves from one reference to a second, unrelated, or inconsistent thing.

For example, in the statement "Our keyboard will teach your mind's eye to play by ear," the speaker has mixed two metaphors, leading to nonsense.

DISCUSSION

However, there are some instances when mixed metaphors work despite themselves somehow. In his song "Little Red Corvette," Prince, a songwriter known for his sexually-charged lyrics, compares the proclivities of a paramour to a fast car and mixes in a metaphor about the use of contraceptives.

"I guess I should've known by the way you parked your car sideways, that it wouldn't last," he sings, before mixing in another metaphor with the line, "See, you're the kinda person that believes in makin' out once—love 'em and leave 'em fast. I guess I must be dumb 'cuz you had a pocket full of horses, Trojan and some of them used."

The latter part of that verse is a mixed metaphor that then becomes an extended metaphor later in the song when Prince references his paramour's past lovers. "I guess I should've closed my eyes when you drove me to the place where your horses run free. 'Cause I felt a little ill when I saw all the pictures of the jockeys that were there before me."

CONCLUSION

I think it would be very difficult to imagine modern life without various metaphorical images and comparisons. We meet metaphors in our daily life, but there are many of them in literature. Metaphors have a very effective effect on the human mind due to emotional colors and images. This is especially well observed in poetry. Metaphor has such a powerful effect on a person that psychologists use it in their practice. They help patients solve mental problems.

They are needed to reveal the various images and essence of events as clearly as possible. The most effective metaphor in poetry is expanded and expressed in the following ways:

1. Indirect communication. It uses a comparative expression or a history that uses a comparison.
2. Speech turns in which words are used figuratively. These words are based on likeness, analogy or comparison.

An extended metaphor unfolds in a successive small passage of text: "In the morning it rains in the morning."

Metaphor could become the purpose of the author and lead the reader to a completely new meaning, a new, unexpected meaning. There are many such metaphors in the works of the classics. Take, for example, Gogol's nose. The very word "nose" took on a metaphorical meaning in his story. William Shakespeare's works are especially rich in metaphors. They give new meaning to characters and events.

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